

A COMMON, OPEN SOURCE INTERFACE
BETWEEN EARTH OBSERVATION DATA
INFRASTRUCTURES AND FRONT-END
APPLICATIONS

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First overview of needed processes from use cases

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List of Acronyms

API Application Programming Interface

BMNT Austrian Federal Ministry for Sustainability and Tourism

CPU Central Processing Unit

DEM Digital Elevation Model

EO Earth Observation

EVI Enhanced Vegetation Index

LIA Local Incidence Angle

NaN Not a Number

NDVI Normalised Difference Vegetation Index

NRT Near Real-Time

RGB Red-Green-Blue; visible range in image processing

SAR Synthetic Aperture Radar

UDF User-Defined Function

WCS Web Coverage Service

WKT Well-Known Text

WMS Web Mapping Service

1. Executive summary

This report covers the requirements of the four openEO use cases to the API and the project's back-ends. The use cases were defined in the project's proposal and represent workflows, already existing and used by different consortium members. To adapt these workflows to the openEO syntax and thus to make them available to the back-end processes, several project meetings were held to specify processes, that have to be implemented for the API and at the back-ends. Additionally, processes and processing aspects were identified, which may help to enrich the use of openEO for potential users and future use cases.

This report lists and describes the result of these project meetings and shall be used during the project's run as a guide of needed implementation. The report does not differentiate between processes already available within the openEO API and back-ends and processes still to be implemented.

2. Requirements for use cases and beyond

2.1. EO data

To ensure the operability of the four use cases defined in the project, Copernicus' EO data of Sentinel-1, -2, and -3 are required in the back-end's infrastructures.

- Sentinel-1 backscatter data are required to be radiometrically calibrated, topographically normalised (orthorectified using a DEM) and outliers or corrupted images shall be removed.
- Sentinel-2 shall be either from top of atmosphere or from surface reflectance with an atmospheric correction and shall include cloud masks. Also here, outliers and corrupted images shall be removed.
- Sentinel-3 shall be either from top of atmosphere or from surface reflectance with an atmospheric correction and shall include cloud masks. Also here, outliers and corrupted images shall be removed.

The four use cases require the EO data either readily available with these characteristics or being processed on demand accordingly, using back-end internal processes. For implementing more flexible workflows using additional user defined data, the EO service providers need also secured personal EO data storage at the back-ends side and a way to access them via openEO.

2.2. Needed processes

Following processes and aspects are either required to be realised using the openEO API to implement the defined use cases, or they present a related potential benefit for the users and thus enhance the possibility of a wide acceptance of openEO.

User authentication: During the project's run a strict user authentication is obstructive for testing purposes. Instead, back-end providers offer momentarily free access to distinct virtual

boxes with EO test data and reduced processing possibilities, but the same processing infrastructure as the complete back-end. For an operational use of back-end providers via openEO a user authentication will be indispensable to guarantee users their own data storage and service providers a business model.

User data management: Users shall be able to upload, store and download their own EO data and products (geocoded masks, raster maps). Not required for any of the defined use cases, but seen as being important is the possibility to upload and store vector files. The ability to store data also includes the possibility to monitor used / available disk space. Additionally, to query about users information as the actual user credit or available CPU is required. The ability to share personal EO data with additional well defined users via openEO could further increase its impact.

Data access: The query of EO raster data shall be possible in a standardised way. This implies a comparable structure of EO metadata, accessible by the users, including a standardised strategy of providing different bands of a dataset. Momentarily, distinct back-end providers store multi-band images as a whole, while others store each band separately. These approaches don't allow a standardised user access to the EO data. The EO data query shall include the possibility to list all available data as well as filtering the data by name or metadata (as e.g. overall accuracy, cloud coverage, ascending or descending orbit and processing level). The possibility is needed to filter the detected data collections by

- the contained features or bands (e.g. polarization VV/VH for SAR data or spectral band for multi or hyperspectral sensors) by name or ID,
- the location (bounding box; clipping to vector data; clipping to administrative boundary lines),
- the acquisition time / time period,
- the available processing level or preprocessing steps as e.g. an atmospheric correction,
- the available metadata and masks as e.g. cloud masks.

Masking: The ability to mask geocoded raster data is needed to change pixel values of data composites, single images or bands to NaN or a distinct value. These masking processes shall depend on specific pixel values, on value ranges and on thresholds. Also masking processes based on external geocoded raster or vector information (e.g. a cloud cover mask or a water layer) or on metadata shall be available.

Image processing / image enhancement: Several zonal and pixel based math operators are essential for the use cases.

Until now, existing EO data are available in different projections at the various back-end infrastructures. An **EO data re-projection** tool is needed to transfer the EO data between (at least the most common) projection, defined by EPSG coded reference systems. The ability of re-projection shall also include geocoded raster and vector data uploaded by the user.

For visualisation purposes, a **contrast enhancement stretch** based on the pixel values is useful to re-scale the image brightness to visualise optimally the image information. This stretch may include user defined linear or non-linear functions as well as automated stretching depending on image statistics. A potential use of color table operations will be discussed during the project's run. The histogram equalisation can re-scale the original brightness values and thus create a uniform distribution of intensities across the range of output values. The possibility of color space reductions of the EO data by merging pixel ranges to discrete colours can also reduce required memory space. Not required for the use cases, but an advancement for visualisation purposes would be the possibility to enhance the contrast in local regions of the EO data to reinforce visual transitions between areas of contrasting brightness (edge enhancement).

Spatial filters are required, recalculating pixel values based on the surrounding pixels. These filters can be pre- or user defined and should cover different kinds of convolution filters (high, low and band pass filters). Also the implementation of adaptive filters as e.g. speckle filters would be an asset.

Not required, but an advantage are **predefined functions** to calculate vegetation indices as NDVI or EVI from different bands of optical EO data without the need of a user definition of the mathematical operation or input bands.

Various **geometric re-scaling** techniques for EO raster data shall be included in openEO. They should include basic down-scaling methods towards fine spatial resolution as e.g. nearest-neighbour, bi-linear interpolation or cubic convolution as well as up-scaling processes as e.g. area-weighted averages or multi-looking.

Also a **temporal re-scaling** will be needed for the use cases. This shall be done by temporal interpolations (e.g. linear, non-linear, splines) between acquisition dates.

Math operations: Raster band math operations have to be provided, where all dimensions of image collections shall be handled equally (as in an EO data-cube). That means, the operations described below shall be available to connect pixel values of different image bands, different geographical position, different acquisition time and from different EO image collections.

Statistical operations as mean, median, minimum or maximum value, standard deviation and percentiles of well-defined acquisition data ranges shall be available. This includes (if possible) the information of the exact origin of the extracted pixel values in space, time, band number etc.

Binary arithmetic operators (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division) are required. As all clients, connected within the project offer the implementation of ternary operators, their realisation within openEO could be an advantage.

Boolean operators as (not) equal, less than, greater than (or equal to) are required as well as logical and or logical or to be able to e.g. mask out pixels.

Zonal statistics are not required by the defined use cases, but can be an asset for potential users. This means the implementation of statistical operations as mentioned above for pixel values in a non-trivial user defined space-time. The pixel domain can be identified by clipping the raster data to a vector dataset or a WKT geometry.

Image mosaicking / maximum value composite: A mosaicking of images with acquisition times from a specific time range (ideally from nearly the same overflight) shall be possible. This

approach should already be available with all back-end providers for creating image composites of several tiles of one sole acquisition date. Enhancing this process to a maximum value compositing of a time range will help avoiding cloud coverage or other regions without valid data. This process will need further discussions during the project's run.

Layer stacking: To allow the download or visualisation of user defined parts of EO images or their production results, a layer stacking process for single datasets is needed. While user definitions shall consider equally all possible dimensions of the EO data collections (as for the math operations), the layer stack process shall merge explicitly a defined amount of input features of one or more image collections. Layer stacking of different EO data and their results into a single composite shall be possible, which includes also the possibility to merge data from different Sentinel missions.

UDFs: Use case 3 (Optical-Radar Forest Monitoring) requires the implementation of several user defined functions. Momentarily identified are functions to clean / smooth times series of distinct pixels and to implement already existing workflows to calculate / use time series [1,2]. Further predefined functions as e.g. the implementation of vegetation indices are described above. Still, future discussions are needed to identify additionally needed custom UDF scripts.

Visualisation: Aside the needed possibility of layer stacking different EO data for a visualisation, also the definition of the data's colour code / legend is crucial. Different possibilities exist to visualise one or three banded data.

- A single band result shall be able to be shown using a grey-scale colour ramp. The possibility to visualise other data dimensions as e.g. the time would be a value adding asset.
- Three band EO data shall be shown using a RGB colour composite. A contrast stretch as described above can further enhance the data visualisation.
- A user or predefined pseudo colour ramp can be used for mapping non-linear or non-wavelength based information as e.g. classification results or vegetation indices.
- Classification results can be displayed using discrete colours, as described above.

Data download: Saving preliminary and final products at the user's personal back-ends storage has to be possible as well as downloading them to a local machine. The back-ends and openEO should support the EO data download in image or vector formats selected by the user and in the very least the most common formats like GeoTIFF, KML or shape files. Additional image formats should be defined during the project's run by including specifications from potential openEO users.

As mentioned above for the image's re-projection, also the downloaded dataset should come in a projection of user choice, defined by the EPSG coded reference systems.

Real time interaction: Calculating larger and potentially time consuming processes, the user requires information about the actual state of the workflow. This entails process monitoring as e.g. possible status requests of running processes or automatic notifications (e.g. per email), when a process is finished, failed or needs further user input. Especially asynchronous workflow execution at the back-ends requires this form of interaction. For processing NRT products as e.g. early warning systems for use case 3, an automated recalculation is conceivable with each newly available EO input data. In that case an automated notification to a specific user defined event would be an asset.

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Appendices

A. Use cases

The openEO proposal [3] describes four different use cases with distinct requirements regarding needed input data and process availability. Their minimum requirements will be listed here as well as related processes with the possibility to broaden up the usability of openEO.

A.1. Use Case 1: Radar image compositing

This use case reflects the adaptation of processes from the SGRT tool (developed at TU Wien) to the openEO API and shall produce monthly and seasonal RGB composites of Sentinel-1 backscatter [4]. Pilot user of this workflow will be the *Austrian Federal Ministry for Sustainability and Tourism (BMNT)*.

The processes depend on the availability of orthorectified SAR data or alternatively the possibility to calculate them at the back-end infrastructure from Level-1 data. The same applies to radiometric calibration, where either the SAR data are offering the backscattering coefficients σ^0 in dB or the back-end service has to provide a function to convert digital numbers of each pixel accordingly. These potential functions would need to provide the following services for Sentinel-1 data.

- Radiometric calibration
- Topographic normalisation (orthorectification), using a well-known DEM
- Removal of outliers and corrupted images
- Image mosaicking of EO data from the same acquisition date
- Reduction of speckle
- Conversion from linear to decibel scale

Using these pre-processed EO data, the following steps will have to be implementable using openEO [3]:

1. Gather all Sentinel-1 observations for different polarisation (e.g. VV, VH) in the period of interest e.g. of one month
2. Perform quality checking and masking of NaN values in the input data
3. Calculate statistics like mean or median on the resulting stack of images
4. Store the products as RGB composites

This workflow, which can be used for land cover monitoring purposes (depending on the used compositing method [5, 6]) leads to following minimum required capabilities of the openEO API and the back-end providers.

- Query of Copernicus Sentinel-1 EO data (including quality layer) based on geographical and temporal information or metadata as e.g. polarisation (VV, VH)

- Masking of information based on pixel values (values above -5 dB are to be set to NaN)
- Contrast stretch of pixel values between specified thresholds (comparable with Python's *bytescale* command)
- Raster based band mathematics operators and basic statistical functions (addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, mean, median)
- Merging well defined bands of a specific acquisition time to a layer stack
- Visualisation of user defined bands (in grey-scale or RGB)
- Download processing results as GeoTIFF or netCDF format

A.2. Use Case 2: Multi-source phenology toolbox

This use case concentrates on data fusion tools [7, 8], time-series generation and phenological metrics using Sentinel-2 data. It will be tested on several back-end platforms by pilot users from the *Action against Hunger* and the *International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development*.

The here tested processes depend on the availability of orthorectified Sentinel-2 surface reflectance data including per pixel quality masks. Alternatively, corresponding to the needed pre-processing steps described in A.1 the following pre-processing steps for Copernicus Sentinel-2 data need to be available at the back-end infrastructures.

- Cloud masking
- Atmospheric correction
- Removal of outliers and corrupted images
- Image mosaicking of EO data from the same acquisition date

Based on these input data, following processes need to be available for the use case.

- Cleaning / smoothing of a time-series of a distinct pixel (potentially using a UDF)
- Calculate maximum / minimum value of a time-series of a distinct pixel including acquisition time of that value
- Band math algorithms needed to compute vegetation indices as EVI
- Per pixel interpolation between acquisition dates (temporal resampling) to generate a daily time-series
- Download resulting time-series as GeoTIFF or netCDF format

Following aspects are seen as not obligatory for the project's success but would help its usability.

- Outlier removal step for the generated time-series
- Pre-built functions (UDFs) as the automated calculation of (or query for automatically provided) vegetation indices

A.3. Use Case 3: Optical–Radar Forest Monitoring

This use case treats the needed processes to identify near-real time forest cover changes through BFAST [1] and / or Bayts [2], developed at WUR. After ensuring the availability of the needed processes for this use case, it shall provide a complex workflow in the form of a user-defined function. The output of this workflow shall be a forest – non-forest map, which will be tested by the *Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations*. Needed input EO data are — as well as in use cases 1 and 2 — orthorectified Sentinel-1 backscattering coefficients and Sentinel-2 surface reflectance data. Additionally to the already described processes, a usage of this use case also requires following.

- Data co-registration, combining Sentinel-1 and -2 datasets into a single time-series
- Applying Bayts or BFAST, possibly as a UDF
- Storing intermediate data or data from previous iterations temporarily in private storage at the back-end’s infrastructure

A.4. Use Case 4: Snow Monitoring with Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-3

This use case covers the subject of detecting snow cover and status, using Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-3 EO data. The original workflows [9–12] are already running internally at EURAC, while the openEO adapted version shall be tested by the *Hydrological Office of the Autonomous Province of Bolzano*. Aside orthorectified and speckle filtered Sentinel-1 data as in use case 1 (VV, VH, LIA), the integration of a snow cover map e.g. derived from medium coarse resolution multispectral sensors like MODIS, Sentinel-3 or NPP-VIIRS will be needed in this use case. Next to the needed processes already mentioned above, openEO has to provide the following functionality.

- Image thresholding for classification, based on standard thresholds that may be modified by users.
- Boolean band operators
- Subsetting of a specific AOI, e.g South Tyrol, hence possibly upload of polygon or transmission via WKT geometry to backend.
- Pre-processing and all image processing steps mentioned above for uploaded EO imagery, e.g. user authentication, data discovery, etc.

Further advantages are seen by the possibility to expose the resulting maps as webservice (wms / wcs) to the user.